

Risk Management Policy

Document Owner: Information Security Manager
Approved By: Information Security Committee
Approval Date: 03/15/2026
Effective Date: 04/01/2026

© 2026 Juan Ruda

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19917605>

This publication is distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

License details: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Description of Changes
1.0	03/15/2026	Stefan Krauss (ISM)	Initial approved version

Table of Contents

1. Purpose.....	4
2. Scope	4
3. Principles	4
4. Risk Methodology.....	4
5. Risk Appetite	5
6. Risk Acceptance Criteria	5
7. Risk Assessment.....	5
8. Risk Register.....	6
9. Risk Treatment.....	6
10. Residual Risk.....	6
11. Governance & Compliance.....	6
11.1. Communication & Awareness.....	6
11.2. Roles and Responsibilities	7
11.3. Review	7
11.4. Exceptions	7
11.5. Non-Compliance	7
11.6. Continual Improvement	8

1. Purpose

The purpose of this policy is to establish the principles and requirements for the management of information security risks within the organization.

2. Scope

This Policy applies to all information security risk management activities conducted in the organization related to information assets within the defined scope of the Information Security Management System (ISMS).

3. Principles

The organization establishes the following principles to guide the protection of information assets and the operation of the Information Security Management System (ISMS):

Risk-based approach: Information security decisions are based on the identification, assessment, and treatment of risks to the organization.

Consistent methodology: Risk management activities are performed using a defined and consistent methodology to ensure repeatability, comparability, and reliability of results.

Business alignment: Risk management supports the organization's strategic objectives and enables informed decision-making by Executive Management.

Accountability and ownership: Risks and associated assets are assigned to designated owners who are responsible for ensuring appropriate risk treatment and monitoring.

4. Risk Methodology

The organization adopts a structured risk management methodology aligned with ISO/IEC 27005 to ensure systematic identification, analysis, evaluation, and treatment of information security risks.

An asset-based risk assessment approach is used, whereby risks are identified in relation to information assets within the scope of the ISMS.

Risk analysis is conducted primarily using a semi-quantitative method. Risks are evaluated using defined qualitative impact and likelihood scales (Low, Moderate, High), supported by assigned numerical values and financial value ranges to enable consistent and comparable risk evaluation.

The detailed criteria, scales, and calculation methods are defined in the Risk Assessment Methodology and supporting documentation.

5. Risk Appetite

The organization adopts a moderate risk appetite in relation to information security risks.

The organization remains growth-oriented while prioritizing sustainable and secure expansion. Risk-taking is permitted where it supports innovation, competitiveness, and business growth; however, risks that could significantly compromise the confidentiality, integrity, or availability of information, regulatory compliance, financial stability, or organizational reputation are not acceptable.

Risk treatment activities should not exceed the potential impact or business value gained from reducing the risk.

6. Risk Acceptance Criteria

The organization may accept risks that, following risk analysis and evaluation, are determined to be at a moderate or lower level, provided they fall within the defined risk appetite.

A risk may be accepted where the estimated economic impact is demonstrably lower than the cost of implementing controls, provided that such acceptance is formally documented and approved in accordance with the organization's risk management procedures.

7. Risk Assessment

Risk assessment is conducted to ensure that information security risks affecting information assets are systematically identified, analyzed, and evaluated.

The organization performs risk assessments at planned intervals and when significant changes occur to systems, processes, technologies, or business operations. The detailed methodology is defined in the “**Risk Assessment Procedure**”.

8. Risk Register

The organization shall maintain a Risk Register as the formal record of identified information security risks.

9. Risk Treatment

Risks that exceed the defined risk acceptance criteria shall be subject to risk treatment.

The objective of risk treatment is to reduce risk to an acceptable level in a manner that is proportionate to the potential impact and aligned with the organization’s risk appetite and business objectives.

Selected risk treatment measures that involve the implementation of information security controls shall be reflected in the Statement of Applicability (SoA).

The detailed risk treatment planning process is defined in the “**Risk Treatment Procedure.**”

10. Residual Risk

Following the implementation of risk treatment actions, risks shall be reassessed to determine the resulting residual risk level.

Residual risks shall be compared against the established risk acceptance criteria. Where residual risk remains above acceptable thresholds, additional treatment shall be considered or the risk shall be formally accepted.

All residual risk decisions shall be formally documented.

11. Governance & Compliance

11.1. Communication & Awareness

This Policy shall be communicated to all employees, contractors, and relevant third parties whose roles involve information security risk management activities within the scope of the ISMS.

The Policy shall be made available through the organization's internal documentation repository and, where appropriate, through contractual or onboarding processes for external parties.

Periodic training and awareness initiatives shall be implemented to ensure personnel understand their role in supporting the organization's risk management framework.

11.2. Roles and Responsibilities

Roles and responsibilities related to information security risk management, including asset ownership, risk ownership, and oversight responsibilities, are defined in the document "Information Security Roles and Responsibilities (FWR-05)".

11.3. Review

This policy shall be reviewed at least annually to ensure its continued suitability, adequacy, and effectiveness.

An earlier review shall be conducted in the event of significant changes to the organization's business model, regulatory environment, risk landscape, or ISMS scope.

The Information Security Manager is responsible for initiating and coordinating the review of this Policy. Any proposed revisions shall be submitted to the Information Security Committee for approval.

11.4. Exceptions

Exceptions to this policy may be granted where justified by legitimate business needs.

Exceptions must be reviewed and approved by the Information Security Committee based on the level of associated residual risk. Approved exceptions shall be documented in the Risk Register and subject to periodic review.

11.5. Non-Compliance

Compliance with this Policy is mandatory for all employees, contractors, and relevant third parties within the scope of the ISMS.

Failure to comply with this Policy may result in corrective actions, which may include disciplinary measures in accordance with internal policies, contractual remedies, or termination of agreements, as applicable.

11.6. Continual Improvement

Performance, audit results, risk assessments, and management reviews shall be used to identify opportunities to enhance the effectiveness, suitability, and adequacy of this policy.